

A Study of the Precipitation of Zirconyl Tungstate

K. N. Sahu

Conductometric study of the reaction between zirconyl chloride and sodium tungstate has been studied by the author in his earlier publication¹. In the present investigation sodium tungstate has been used as a precipitating agent for the quantitative estimation of zirconium.

Solutions were prepared by dissolving A.R. (B.D.H.) samples of zirconyl chloride and sodium tungstate in double distilled water. Conductance measurements were done with a "Doron" conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell, and a 1000 cycle WTW oscillator at 28°.

Conductometric study: 50 ml solutions of $M/100$, $M/125$, and $M/150$ zirconyl chloride were conductometrically titrated against $M/10$ Na-tungstate solution. These titrations were carried out both without and with varying amounts of absolute alcohol, but there was absolutely no difference in titre values, which shows that the compound formed in the reaction does not hydrolyse. Clear breaks are obtained in the plot of conductance against

volume of sodium tungstate added (fig. 1). The titre values of Na_2WO_4 calculated from the positions of the break in the graph (5 ml, 4 ml, and 3.3 ml respectively for the three

1. K. N. Sahu, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 221.

solutions) agree well with the calculated values (5 ml 4 ml, and 3.33 ml) respectively) for the stoichiometric reaction :

Gravimetric study : The precipitation of the compound is complete when heated to boiling with excess of Na-tungstate and allowed to settle. A weighed quantity of the precipitated solid was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and analysed for zirconium². The experiment was repeated thrice with varying quantities of zirconyl chloride started with (namely, 0.3223 gm, 0.4834 gm and 0.8057 gm). The weights-percent of Zr as found in the precipitates (24.1, 23.9 and 25.9% respectively) correspond well with the theoretical value required for the assumed composition of the precipitated compound as ZrO(WO₄).

Since tungstate ion precipitates many other metallic ions, therefore the use of this method for the estimation of zirconium is limited to the case when it is present alone.

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Chemical Laboratory,
Birla Institute of Technology,
Mesra, Ranchi, Bihar.

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2. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1953, page. 477.